

Bromate—Bromide Mixture as a Titrimetric Reagent for the Determination of some *ortho*-Hydroxyaldehydes, Acids, Hydrazides, Schiff Bases and their Metal Complexes

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The quantitative determination of salicylaldehyde, 5-chloro-, 5-bromo-, 5-nitro-, 5-methoxy-, 5-hydroxy-, 4-methoxy-, 4-hydroxy-, 3-methoxy-, 3-ethoxy-, 3-hydroxy- and 3,5-dichloro-salicylaldehydes, and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, salicylic acid, 5-chloro-, 5-bromo-, 5-nitro-, 5-hydroxy-, 4-hydroxy-, 3-hydroxy-, and 3,5-dichloro-salicylic acids, Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehydes and *o*-aminophenol, 3-aminothiophenol, benzoylhydrazide and salicylhydrazide, and metal complexes of these Schiff bases with dioxouranium(VI) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) have been carried out by bromometric titration technique using 0.1 N KBrO₃ - 0.1 N KBr solution. In general, the bromination takes place at the *ortho*- and *para*-positions with respect to the OH group in the ring. If one of the positions is pre-occupied by another group, bromination takes place at the other vacant position. The effects of the substituents present in the ring, temperature, time and solvent on the bromination of the compounds are discussed.

In acidic medium potassium bromate behaves as an oxidising agent and oxidises bromide ions to molecular bromine ;

The liberated bromine may be used to brominate the aromatic compounds. The method avoids the possible hazards of using molecular bromine. In the bromination of organic compounds the use of a mixture of KBrO₃ - KBr solution has also been suggested¹. In the course of our study on the Schiff bases and their metal complexes we thought it worthwhile to determine quantitatively the Schiff bases in their metal complexes using KBrO₃ - KBr titration technique. We report in this paper the quantitative determination of the Schiff bases (1) derived from salicylaldehyde or substituted-salicylaldehydes and *o*-aminophenol, 3-aminothiophenol,

R = H, 5-Cl, 5-Br, 5-NO₂, 5-OMe, 4-OMe, 3-OMe, 3-OEt, 3,5-(Cl)₂ and 5,6-Bz ;
R' = C₆H₄-OH, C₆H₄-SH, NH-CO-C₆H₄-OH

benzoylhydrazide or salicylhydrazide using bromometric titration. The coordinated Schiff bases in dioxouranium(VI) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes and the coordinated *o*-phenylenediamine, 3-aminopyridine, 2,2'-dipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline in dioxouranium(VI) heterochelates and coordinated tetrahydrofuran in dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes have been determined using this technique. In the course of this study it was necessary to estimate quantitatively salicylaldehyde, substituted-salicylaldehydes and their oxidation products by this method.

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde was procured from Sarabhai M. Chem. Co. 5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde, benzoylhydrazide, salicylhydrazide and the Schiff bases were prepared according to the published procedures²⁻⁵. Salicylaldehyde (S. Merck), 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 4-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 3-ethoxysalicylaldehyde, *o*-aminophenol, 3-aminothiophenol, 2,2'-dipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline (all Aldrich), 3-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and *o*-phenylenediamine (all Fluka, A.G.) were used. Potassium bromate, potassium bromide and all other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

General method of syntheses of substituted-dihydroxybenzaldehydes : 3-Methoxy-, 4-methoxy-,

5-methoxy- or 3-ethoxy-salicylaldehyde (0.01 mol) was suspended in water (20 ml) containing sodium hydroxide (0.80 g, 0.02 mol). The mixture was boiled on a water-bath for 1 h and a clear yellow solution was obtained. The solution was poured slowly to 1:1 H₂O-concentrated HCl solution (100 ml) and kept at 0°. An oily layer settled at the bottom which was separated by decantation and treated with ethanol (2 ml) and when a white precipitate was obtained. It was suction-filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised from ethanol, and dried in vacuum, (~20%).

Procedure for the quantitative determination of compounds :

Ortho-hydroxy aromatic aldehydes : R-Salicylaldehyde (R=3-OMe, 4-OMe, 5-OMe, 3-OEt ; Table 1) was dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) or R-salicylaldehyde (R=H, 5-Cl, 5-Br, 5-NO₂, 3,5-(Cl)₂, 5,6-Bz) was boiled with 0.1 N NaOH (20 ml) for 1 h. The solution was transferred to a stoppered iodine flask which was allowed to reach a fixed temperature (Table 1). A 0.1 N KBrO₃-0.1 N KBr solution (40 ml) was added to the flask and was shaken for 2 min. The mixture was acidified with 2.5 N HCl (50 ml) and the flask was shaken vigorously for a fixed time and temperature (Table 1). The unreacted bromine was titrated iodometrically with 0.1 N Na₂S₂O₃ solution to the starch end-point.

Ortho-hydroxy aromatic carboxylic acids, o-aminophenol, 3-aminothiophenol, benzoylhydrazide, salicylhydrazide, o-phenylenediamine, 3-aminopyridine, 2,2'-dipyridyl, o-phenanthroline and tetrahydrofuran : The appropriate compound (Table 2) was dissolved

in ethanol (10 ml). The experimental procedure adopted was similar to the previous method. The experiment was carried out at room temperature (25°).

Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde or substituted-salicylaldehydes and o-aminophenol, 3-aminothiophenol, benzoylhydrazide or salicylhydrazide and their metal complexes : The appropriate Schiff base (1) (Table 2) or the metal complex was boiled with 0.1 N NaOH (50 ml) for 1 h and filtered. In case of the compounds where R=3-OMe, 3-OEt, 4-OMe, 5-OMe or the metal complex, the compound was dissolved in ethanol (20 ml). The experimental procedure adopted was similar to the previous method, and was carried out at room temperature (25°).

Results and Discussion

The quantitative determination of salicylaldehyde or substituted-salicylaldehydes has been carried out in acidic medium by brominating the aldehyde in ethanol or in an aqueous sodium hydroxide medium at 0-25° with a solution containing an excess of 0.1 N KBrO₃-0.1 N KBr and then titrating the unreacted bromine with standard sodium thiosulphate solution. The bromination of all other compounds were done at 25°. A typical reaction is depicted below,

TABLE 1—BROMOMETRIC TITRATION DATA OF AN ETHANOLIC SOLUTION OF SALICYLALDEHYDE AND SUBSTITUTED-SALICYLALDEHYDES

Compd.	Wt. of compd. g	Consumed Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ solution* ml	Consumed 0.1 N KBrO ₃ -0.1 N KBr solution ml	Time, min (Temp., °C)	Equiv. bromine atom per mol of compd. Found(Calcd.)	Ligand Found %
Salicylaldehyde	0.0970	33.0	30.8	15(10)	3.88(4.00)	99.84
5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde	0.0670	9.1	8.5	30(15)	1.99(2.00)	99.77
5-Bromosalicylaldehyde	0.0981	9.3	8.7	30(15)	1.98(2.00)	100.25
5-Nitrosalicylaldehyde	0.0918	11.6	10.8	10(0)	1.97(2.00)	99.73
5-Methoxysalicylaldehyde	0.0954	13.1	12.2	10(0)	1.95(2.00)	99.68
5-Hydroxysalicylaldehyde	0.0708	10.8	10.1	30(5)	1.97(2.00)	99.93
4-Methoxysalicylaldehyde	0.0638	17.8	16.6	25(10)	3.96(4.00)	99.87
4-Hydroxysalicylaldehyde	0.1076	32.6	30.5	45(15)	3.91(4.00)	100.04
3-Methoxysalicylaldehyde	0.0772	10.7	10.0	10(0)	1.97(2.00)	99.94
3-Ethoxysalicylaldehyde	0.0865	11.0	10.3	15(0)	1.97(2.00)	100.34
3-Hydroxysalicylaldehyde	0.0825	12.5	11.7	30(5)	1.95(2.00)	100.36
3,5-Dichlorosalicylaldehyde	0.0602	0.0	0.0	30(10)	0.00(2.00)	0
2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde	0.1050	35.4	35.9	20(20)	5.88(6.00)	100.01
Salicylaldehyde	0.0630	33.5	31.3	120(30)	6.06(6.00)	100.02
5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde	0.0802	21.6	20.2	60(25)	3.94(4.00)	100.04
5-Bromosalicylaldehyde	0.0732	15.5	14.5	60(25)	3.98(4.00)	100.04
5-Nitrosalicylaldehyde	0.1018	25.4	23.7	90(25)	3.89(4.00)	99.94
3-Methoxysalicylaldehyde	0.0890	24.7	23.1	90(25)	3.94(4.00)	100.13
4-Methoxysalicylaldehyde	0.0854	36.2	33.8	120(25)	6.02(6.00)	99.93
5-Methoxysalicylaldehyde	0.1192	33.0	30.8	60(25)	3.93(4.00)	99.94
3-Ethoxysalicylaldehyde	0.0853	21.4	20.0	60(25)	3.89(4.00)	100.05
3,5-Dichlorosalicylaldehyde	0.1120	12.4	11.6	120(25)	1.98(2.00)	99.91
2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde	0.0831	39.8	37.2	180(25)	7.69(8.00)	100.12

*Normality of Na₂S₂O₃ solution used = 0.09945 N.

TABLE 2—BROMOMETRIC TITRATION DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compd.*	Wt. of compd. g	Consumed Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ solution** ml	Consumed 0.1 N KBrO ₃ - 0.1 N KBr solution ml	Time, min (Temp., °C)	Equiv. bromine per mole of compound Found(Calcd.)	Ligand % Found/(Calcd.)
Salicylic acid	0.0660	90.1	28.1	45(25)	5.88(6.00)	99.92
5-Chlorosalicylic acid	0.0645	15.8	14.8	60(25)	3.97(4.00)	100.28
5-Bromosalicylic acid	0.0735	14.2	18.3	60(25)	3.92(4.00)	100.17
5-Nitrosalicylic acid	0.0904	20.8	19.4	45(25)	3.93(4.00)	99.92
5-Hydroxysalicylic acid	0.0996	26.8	25.0	60(25)	3.87(4.00)	99.88
4-Hydroxysalicylic acid	0.0730	29.6	27.7	30(25)	5.84(6.00)	100.06
3-Hydroxysalicylic acid	0.0638	17.3	16.2	60(25)	3.90(4.00)	100.26
3,5-Dichlorosalicylic acid	0.1000	10.2	9.5	30(25)	1.98(2.00)	99.79
o-Aminophenol	0.0980	38.4	35.9	45(25)	3.99(4.00)	100.07
3-Aminothiophenol	0.0602	30.3	28.3	60(25)	5.88(6.00)	99.93
Benzoylhydrazide	0.0878	40.3	37.7	45(25)	5.83(6.00)	100.16
Salicylhydrazide	0.0746	31.6	29.5	60(25)	6.02(6.00)	99.84
o-Phenylenediamine	0.0948	18.6	17.4	60(25)	1.98(2.00)	100.11
3-Aminopyridine	0.0613	13.8	12.9	60(25)	1.98(2.00)	99.90
2,2'-Dipyridyl	0.1064	29.0	27.1	60(25)	3.97(4.00)	100.08
o-Phenanthroline	0.0693	24.7	23.1	90(25)	5.99(6.00)	100.17
Tetrahydrofuran	0.0882	26.2	24.5	45(25)	1.99(2.00)	100.50
Sal-OAP	0.0837	42.0	39.3	60(25)	9.99(10.00)	100.11
5-Chlorosal-OAP	0.0996	34.0	31.8	45(25)	7.89(8.00)	100.15
5-Bromosal-OAP	0.0731	21.2	19.8	40(25)	7.91(8.00)	99.99
5-Nitrosal-OAP	0.1154	38.0	35.5	60(25)	7.94(8.00)	99.96
Hydroxy-OAP	0.0629	30.1	28.1	120(25)	11.76(12.00)	99.91
Sal-3-ATP	0.0682	38.2	35.7	120(25)	11.99(12.00)	99.98
5-Chlorosal-3-ATP	0.0680	27.7	25.9	90(25)	10.09(10.00)	100.06
5-Bromosal-3-ATP	0.0840	28.9	27.0	90(25)	9.90(10.00)	99.99
5-Nitrosal-3-ATP	0.0623	24.6	22.9	90(25)	10.11(10.00)	99.62
5-Methoxysal-3-ATP	0.0753	30.4	28.4	120(25)	9.77(10.00)	99.98
4-Methoxysal-3-ATP	0.0744	35.8	33.5	120(25)	11.65(12.00)	100.10
3-Methoxysal-3-ATP	0.0872	35.4	33.1	120(25)	9.83(10.00)	100.01
Hydroxy-3-ATP	0.0740	39.5	36.9	150(25)	13.97(14.00)	99.94
Sal-BHZ	0.0716	37.8	35.3	90(25)	11.84(12.00)	99.93
5-Chlorosal-BHZ	0.0694	27.0	25.2	90(25)	10.63(10.00)	99.91
5-Bromosal-BHZ	0.0803	26.3	24.6	60(25)	9.76(10.00)	100.13
5-Nitrosal-BHZ	0.0698	25.5	23.8	45(25)	9.73(10.00)	99.87
5-Methoxysal-BHZ	0.0869	33.8	31.6	60(25)	9.81(10.00)	100.08
4-Methoxysal-BHZ	0.0613	28.3	26.5	60(25)	11.65(12.00)	100.19
3-Methoxysal-BHZ	0.0750	29.2	27.3	45(25)	9.82(10.00)	100.08
3-Ethoxysal-BHZ	0.0723	27.0	25.2	60(25)	9.91(10.00)	99.88
3,5-Dichlorosal-BHZ	0.0696	19.0	17.8	90(25)	7.88(8.00)	100.28
Hydroxy-BHZ	0.0738	37.3	34.9	120(25)	13.69(14.00)	100.17
Sal-SHZ	0.0728	36.6	34.2	120(25)	12.03(12.00)	99.97
5-Chlorosal-SHZ	0.1100	39.6	37.0	90(25)	10.38(10.00)	99.97
5-Bromosal-SHZ	0.1158	36.9	34.5	60(25)	9.98(10.00)	100.00
5-Nitrosal-SHZ	0.0702	24.7	23.1	60(25)	9.89(10.00)	100.15
5-Methoxysal-SHZ	0.0628	23.0	21.5	30(25)	9.79(10.00)	100.01
4-Methoxysal-SHZ	0.0921	40.8	38.1	40(25)	11.84(12.00)	99.92
3-Methoxysal-SHZ	0.1066	39.0	36.5	30(25)	9.78(10.00)	100.13
3-Ethoxysal-SHZ	0.0878	30.8	28.8	45(25)	9.89(10.00)	100.16
3,5-Dichlorosal-SHZ	0.1155	30.0	28.0	120(25)	7.89(8.00)	99.86
Hydroxy-SHZ	0.0633	30.7	28.7	120(25)	13.87(14.00)	100.03
UO ₂ (sal-3-ATP) ₂	0.0738	16.5	15.4	240(25)	24.18(24.00)	63.00(62.81)
UO ₂ (3-methoxysal-3-ATP) ₂	0.0841	15.1	14.1	180(25)	20.09(20.00)	65.86(65.65)
UO ₂ (4-methoxysal-3-ATP) ₂	0.0983	20.9	19.5	240(25)	23.79(24.00)	65.83(65.65)
UO ₂ (5-methoxysal-3-ATP) ₂	0.0933	16.7	15.6	180(25)	20.00(20.00)	65.91(65.65)
UO ₂ (sal-3-ATP) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	0.0986	16.1	15.1	120(25)	24.19(24.00)	53.94(53.76)
UO ₂ (hydroxy-3-ATP) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	0.0712	13.1	12.2	240(25)	27.95(28.00)	58.41(58.61)
UO ₂ (sal-3-ATP)(NO ₂) ₂ (bipy)	0.0585	7.5	7.0	240(25)	15.98(16.00)	53.71(53.63)
UO ₂ (sal-3-ATP)(NO ₂) ₂ (ophen)	0.0698	10.0	9.4	270(25)	17.97(18.00)	55.57(55.13)
UO ₂ (sal-SHZ).CH ₃ OH	0.0967	10.2	9.5	180(25)	11.99(12.00)	45.89(45.68)
UO ₂ (5-chlorosal-SHZ).CH ₃ OH	0.0932	8.3	7.8	150(25)	10.07(10.00)	49.45(48.86)
UO ₂ (5-bromosal-SHZ).CH ₃ OH	0.0734	6.4	5.9	150(25)	9.86(10.00)	52.07(52.44)
UO ₂ (5-methoxysal-SHZ).CH ₃ OH	0.0794	7.0	6.5	180(25)	9.96(10.00)	48.48(48.46)
UO ₂ (3-methoxysal-SHZ).CH ₃ OH	0.0628	5.5	5.1	180(25)	9.91(10.00)	48.41(48.46)
UO ₂ (3-ethoxysal-SHZ).CH ₃ OH	0.0951	8.4	7.9	180(25)	9.98(10.00)	50.31(49.67)
UO ₂ (3,5-dichlorosal-SHZ).CH ₃ OH	0.0955	6.8	6.4	210(25)	8.06(8.00)	52.35(51.68)
UO ₂ (hydroxy-SHZ).CH ₃ OH	0.0605	7.5	7.0	240(25)	14.02(14.00)	50.43(50.17)
UO ₂ (sal-SHZ)(en)	0.0979	9.3	8.7	150(25)	11.91(12.00)	43.89(43.49)
UO ₂ (sal-SHZ)(tn)	0.0943	8.6	8.0	150(25)	12.01(12.00)	42.63(42.47)
UO ₂ (sal-SHZ)(bn)	0.0776	6.8	6.4	150(25)	12.08(12.00)	42.12(41.50)

(Table 2 contd.)

UO ₂ (sal-SHZ)(hn)	0.0907	7.2	6.7	150(25)	11.96(12.00)	39.89(39.69)
UO ₂ (sal-SHZ)(phen)	0.0770	10.4	9.7	240(25)	13.93(14.00)	57.48(57.28)
UO ₂ (sal-SHZ)(ampy)	0.0913	12.6	11.8	180(25)	14.16(14.00)	56.74(56.31)
UO ₂ (sal-SHZ)(bipy)	0.0841	12.6	11.8	240(25)	15.79(16.00)	60.72(60.28)
UO ₂ (sal-SHZ)(ophen)	0.0836	14.1	13.2	270(25)	18.01(18.00)	62.05(61.65)
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(en)	0.1007	9.5	8.9	120(25)	11.95(12.00)	42.36(41.90)
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(tn)	0.0918	8.4	7.9	120(25)	12.18(12.00)	41.51(40.89)
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(bn)	0.0795	6.7	6.3	120(25)	11.77(12.00)	40.52(39.93)
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(hn)	0.0926	7.2	6.7	120(25)	11.89(12.00)	38.31(38.14)
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(phen)	0.0666	9.1	8.5	180(25)	14.01(14.00)	56.45(56.17)
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(ampy)	0.0744	10.2	9.5	150(25)	13.99(14.00)	55.32(55.15)
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(bipy)	0.0767	11.6	10.8	180(25)	15.82(16.00)	59.41(59.34)
UO ₂ (sal-BHZ)(ophen)	0.0986	16.8	15.7	210(25)	18.03(18.00)	61.05(60.76)
MoO ₃ (sal-BHZ).H ₂ O	0.1006	20.7	19.4	120(25)	11.92(12.00)	62.69(61.98)
MoO ₃ (5-chlorosal-BHZ).H ₂ O	0.0769	12.8	11.9	60(25)	9.99(10.00)	65.26(65.11)
MoO ₃ (5-bromosal-BHZ).H ₂ O	0.0787	12.5	11.7	60(25)	10.03(10.00)	69.03(68.47)
MoO ₃ (5-nitrosal-BHZ).H ₂ O	0.0947	15.5	14.5	120(25)	9.94(10.00)	66.52(65.97)
MoO ₃ (hydroxy-BHZ).H ₂ O	0.0983	22.6	21.1	180(25)	14.06(14.00)	66.75(66.36)
MoO ₃ (sal-SHZ).H ₂ O	0.0841	17.2	16.1	150(25)	12.04(12.00)	64.10(63.50)
MoO ₃ (5-chlorosal-SHZ).H ₂ O	0.0665	11.0	10.3	120(25)	10.11(10.00)	66.96(66.39)
MoO ₃ (5-bromosal-SHZ).H ₂ O	0.0896	13.8	12.9	120(25)	9.92(10.00)	69.92(69.52)
MoO ₃ (5-nitrosal-SHZ).H ₂ O	0.0633	10.2	9.5	120(25)	9.98(10.00)	67.42(67.19)
MoO ₃ (3-methoxysal-SHZ).H ₂ O	0.1026	17.0	15.9	90(25)	10.08(10.00)	66.54(66.05)
MoO ₃ (3-ethoxysal-SHZ).H ₂ O	0.0983	16.0	14.9	120(25)	10.06(10.00)	67.32(67.12)
MoO ₃ (3,5-dichlorosal-SHZ).H ₂ O	0.1058	13.2	12.3	180(25)	7.94(8.00)	69.06(68.87)
MoO ₃ (hydroxy-SHZ).H ₂ O	0.0985	22.1	20.7	240(25)	13.98(14.00)	68.13(67.66)
MoO ₃ (sal-BHZ).THF	0.0670	16.3	15.2	180(25)	14.08(14.00)	71.06(70.78)
MoO ₃ (5-chlorosal-BHZ).THF	0.0672	13.2	12.3	120(25)	11.92(12.00)	73.11(72.91)
MoO ₃ (5-bromosal-BHZ).THF	0.0874	16.5	15.4	150(25)	12.12(12.00)	75.50(75.24)
MoO ₃ (5-nitrosal-BHZ).THF	0.1078	21.4	20.0	180(25)	12.19(12.00)	73.95(73.49)
MoO ₃ (hydroxy-BHZ).THF	0.0681	17.8	16.6	180(25)	16.17(16.00)	74.03(73.77)
MoO ₃ (sal-SHZ).THF	0.0985	23.5	21.9	180(25)	14.10(14.00)	72.06(71.81)
MoO ₃ (5-chlorosal-SHZ).THF	0.0916	17.7	16.5	150(25)	11.95(12.00)	74.04(73.79)
MoO ₃ (5-bromosal-SHZ).THF	0.0843	15.3	14.3	180(25)	11.91(12.00)	76.35(75.98)
MoO ₃ (5-nitrosal-SHZ).THF	0.0672	12.8	11.9	150(25)	11.96(12.00)	74.37(74.35)
MoO ₃ (3-methoxysal-SHZ).THF	0.0601	11.8	11.0	120(25)	12.07(12.00)	73.81(73.55)
MoO ₃ (3-ethoxysal-SHZ).THF	0.0696	13.2	12.3	150(25)	11.88(12.00)	74.49(74.29)
MoO ₃ (3,5-dichlorosal-SHZ).THF	0.0939	14.5	13.6	180(25)	9.99(10.00)	76.23(75.53)
MoO ₃ (hydroxy-SHZ).THF	0.0645	16.0	14.9	240(25)	15.67(16.00)	74.72(74.60)

*sal = salicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosal = 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 5-bromosal = 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosal = 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, 5-methoxysal = 5-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 4-methoxysal = 4-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 3-methoxysal = 3-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 3-ethoxysal = 3-ethoxysalicylaldehyde, 3,5-dichlorosal = 3,5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde, hydroxy = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, OAP = orthoaminophenol, ATP = 3-aminothiophenol, BHZ = benzoylhydrazide, SHZ = salicylhydrazide, en = ethylenediamine, tn = trimethylenediamine, bn = tetramethylenediamine, hn = hexamethylenediamine, phen = orthophenylenediamine, ampy = 3-aminopyridine, bipy = 2,2'-bipyridyl, ophen = orthophenanthaline and THF = tetrahydrofuran. **Na₂S₂O₈ solution used = 0.09345 N.

Effect of temperature and substituents: The nucleophilic attack of bromine at the benzene ring is governed by the group orientation effect of the substituent already present in the benzene ring. Francis and Hill⁶ reported that bromine reacts with salicylaldehyde at 10° and forms a dibromoderivative, while at 40° a tribromo derivative is formed. The formation of the dibromo derivative takes place at lower temperature since bromine does not attack the CHO group at lower temperature. We have also studied the bromination at various temperatures and observed that at 10° salicylaldehyde forms a dibromo derivative and at 30° it forms a tribromo derivative. The aldehydes having substitution at 3- or 5-position form the 5- or 3-bromo derivative, respectively. 3,5-Dichlorosalicylaldehyde does not undergo bromination at 10° while the compound reacts with 1 mol of bromine at 25° to form the monobromo derivative, suggesting that at 25° bromine attacks the CHO group.

Freyer⁷ noticed that salicylic acid reacts with an excess of bromine and forms tribromophenol

bromide, which reacts with KI to form potassium salt of tribromophenol with the liberation of iodine.

Francis and Hill⁶ reported that salicylic acid forms the dibromo and tribromo derivatives at -5 and 20°, respectively. The formation of the latter indicates that at 20° bromine attacks the COOH group of salicylic acid. We have also studied the bromination at various temperatures (0-25°) but always noticed that salicylic acid forms only the tribromo derivative. Other substituted-salicylic acids show similar behaviour towards bromination.

Aroylhydrazone undergoes oxidation⁸ with an acidic bromate solution and forms the corresponding carboxylic acid,

The acid thus formed undergoes bromination similar to the corresponding aldehyde. Benzoylhydrazide or salicylhydrazide consumes six equivalents of bromine. The equivalent of bromine per mole

of *o*-aminophenol, 3-aminothiophenol, *o*-phenylenediamine, 3-aminopyridine, 2,2'-dipyridyl, *o*-phenanthroline and tetrahydrofuran is of the order, 2, 4, 2, 2, 4, 6 and 2, suggesting the formation of mono-, di-, mono-, mono-, di-, tri- and mono-bromo derivative, respectively.

Effect of solvent : Salicylaldehyde or substituted-salicylaldehydes were brominated in ethanol or in aqueous sodium hydroxide medium. The results indicate that under similar conditions of temperature and time (Table 1), the aldehyde **1** (R = H, 5-Cl, 5-Br, 5-NO₂, 3,5-(Cl)₂ or 5,6-Bz) always gives the same result irrespective of the nature of the solvent used. On the other hand, the aldehyde **1** (R = 3-OEt, 3-OMe, 4-OMe or 5-OMe) shows different results in the solvents ethanol and aqueous sodium hydroxide. The analytical results indicate that the alkoxy group in these alkoxy-salicylaldehydes undergoes alkaline hydrolysis and forms the corresponding hydroxysalicylaldehydes. These substituted-hydroxysalicylaldehydes show similar behaviour towards bromination as the corresponding alkoxy-salicylaldehyde.

The Schiff bases and the dioxouranium(VI) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes of these Schiff bases react with hot aqueous solution of sodium

hydroxide to form water-soluble sodium salts of the corresponding aldehyde and amine. A mixture of the free ligands is formed upon acidification with 2.5 N HCl, which undergoes bromination with KBrO₃ - KBr solution.

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